

Monetizing Data in International Data Spaces: Business Concepts and Technical Enablers

Contributing Organisations

**INTERNATIONAL DATA
SPACES ASSOCIATION**

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Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
ERC	Ethereum Request for Comments
EU	European Union
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Associations
PAT	Pricing Advisory Tool
REST	Representational State Transfer

1 Introduction

1.1 Monetizing Data within Data Spaces: Background and Rationale

In recent years, the proliferation of digital supply chains and the rising needs for trusted data exchange across supply chain partner have given rise to the emerging of the Data Spaces concepts. Data spaces are decentralized data management infrastructures, which enable data management and data exchange across different value chain partners who adhere to a common set of standards and approaches to storing, sharing and managing data of their value chain. Several international organizations (e.g., the International Data Spaces Associations (IDSA), the FIWARE foundation and the GAIA-X initiative) have introduced the need of data spaces and defined the main technical and non-technical components that comprise a data space. For instance, GAIA-X defines a data space as “*a type of data relationship between trusted partners who adhere to the same high standards and guidelines when it comes to data storage and sharing*”.

The development, deployment and operation of data spaces hinges on several technical/technological and operational/governance building blocks, which span different areas and functionalities, including for example users’ authentication and authorization data interoperability, data processing, data analytics and more. Data spaces implementations come with specific implementation instances of such building blocks, which facilitate the sovereign exchange of data assets across data spaces participants. They also enable the use of the data assets in the scope of different applications.

One of the not so common functionalities of state-of-the-art data spaces implementation concerns data monetization. This is a lost opportunity given that data monetization approaches can be very important for the successful operation of data spaces. Specifically, monetizing data in data space can incentivize organizations to participate in a data space by offering them the potential to generate economic value from their data assets. This process involves transforming data from a mere operational byproduct into a valuable commodity that can be traded, shared, or sold, in ways that create new revenue streams. The rationale behind this monetization is rooted on the fact that data is an asset in the digital economy. As organizations are participating in data spaces to leverage shared data assets towards enhancing their services, improve their decision-making, and foster innovation development, it makes sense to monetize data assets. In this context, modern data spaces can offer a collaborative environment that reduces the dominance of large monopolistic players through the creation of a level playing field where smaller organizations can compete based on the quality of their data assets and data services rather than the sheer volume of data they control.

Data spaces facilitate the monetization of critical data assets by providing a structured environment for data exchange, which is typically supported by governance frameworks that ensure data sovereignty, interoperability, and trust among participants. These frameworks allow organizations to maintain control over their data and to decide how and when it is accessed and used. Moreover, they enable organizations to benefit from collective insights generated through shared data. Thus, the establishment of data marketplaces within these spaces can further enhance monetization opportunities. Specifically, the operators of these marketplaces can act as intermediaries that connect data providers with consumers, which simplifies the process of data trading. This setup encourages more organizations to share their data, while helping them to overcome traditional barriers related to data privacy and security.

Data monetization can also play an important role in fostering the long-term sustainability and wider use of data spaces. This is because it can create tangible economic incentives for participation and collaboration. Once organizations become able to derive monetary value from their data, they are more willing to contribute their data assets to data spaces, which enriches relevant ecosystems with

diverse and high-quality data. This not only enhances the utility and attractiveness of the data space but also ensures its sustainability based on a self-reinforcing cycle of data sharing and value creation. Furthermore, monetization mechanisms and infrastructures such as data marketplaces facilitate the trading of data and helps the establishment of data markets where data and data services are sold at fair and acceptable prices.

1.2 Building Blocks for Data Monetization in Data Spaces

1.2.1 Building Blocks Overview

The design, development and deployment of data spaces relies on the implementation of several foundational building blocks that ensure their effective operation. This building blocks concept is generally in-line with the most reference models for data spaces architecture such as the IDS Reference Architecture Model, which outlines the technical, functional, and organizational requirements for sovereign data sharing. For example, the IDS reference model specifies the use of IDS Connectors for secure data exchange, identity providers for authentication, and brokers for data discovery and management. Moreover, data spaces incorporate decentralized protocols to enhance data privacy and sovereignty, which is very important for data trading with confidence. The integration and customization of the above-mentioned building blocks and protocols enables data spaces to support innovative business models and open new revenue streams.

Data spaces' building blocks can be broadly categorized into technical and governance components. Technical building blocks include data interoperability, data sovereignty, and data value creation. For example, technical building blocks for data interoperability involves the use of semantic models, data formats, and APIs to facilitate seamless data exchange, ensuring that data can be shared and utilized across different systems and platforms. Data sovereignty and trust are established through mechanisms for identifying participants and assets, as well as defining and enforcing policies for access and usage control. This ensures that data providers retain control over their data, fostering trust among participants. Also, data value creation is enabled by registering and discovering data offerings or services, which allows participants to create value-added services and monetize their data assets effectively. Governance building blocks are also essential for establishing a structured environment for data spaces. These include frameworks for data governance, which define the roles and responsibilities of participants, as well as the rules for data sharing and exchange. Governance structures ensure that data spaces operate within legal and ethical boundaries, addressing concerns such as data privacy, security, and compliance with regulations.

1.2.2 Building Blocks for Data Monetization

Most data spaces architectures and implementations account for the need to implement data monetization mechanism by offering building blocks that can be customized to support data monetization. As a prominent example, the Data Spaces Support Centre specifies “Data Value” building blocks, which address the economic aspects of data and enable treating data as an asset. They facilitate data monetization by providing functions for pricing, selling, and exchanging data. This includes developing strategies for data wrapping, bartering, and selling, as well as addressing challenges like privacy and security

As another important example, the International Data Spaces (IDS) Information Model provides a comprehensive framework for managing data in a secure and standardized manner. It addresses several aspects of data management, including data auditing, data accounting, data trading, and data

monetization. Some of the key building blocks and information relevant to these processes within the IDS Information Model, including: (i) **Data Auditing components and parameters** such as “Audit Guarantee” that supports local audit logging and remote audit log tracing for external audit verification, as well as “Integrity Protection and Verification”, which targets the integrity of the software stack and includes local integrity protection and remote integrity verification; (ii) **Data Accounting components and parameters** such as “Usage Control” that define how data can be used, shared, and accessed, as well as logging agreements that specify the logging requirements for data usage towards tracking and accounting for data transactions; (iii) **Data Trading components and parameters** such as “Broker” that acts as a registry for data assets and “Contract Offer and Agreement”, which includes mechanisms for creating and managing contracts such as offers, requests, and agreements between parties; (iv) **Data Monetization components and parameters** such as the “Commodization View” that models the "commodity" aspects of a resource, such as pricing, licensing models, and usage restrictions, and **Pricing Strategies** that supports various pricing strategies such as free, freemium, pay-per-use, and flat rate. The above-listed components and parameters of the IDS Information Model provides a structured and sound approach for managing data value and implementing data trading and monetization mechanisms.

The iShare Data Spaces architecture is another data spaces framework designed to facilitate data exchange in a secure and trusted manner. It includes several building blocks that facilitate the implementation of data markets, including data trading, data auditing, and data monetization. Here's a more detailed look at these components within the iShare architecture: (i) **Data Trading** within iShare is facilitated through a structured framework that provides the necessary legal, functional, operational, and technical specifications to enable seamless data trading. The use of standardized APIs and identity management systems ensures that data trading is both secure and interoperable across different platforms and organizations; (ii) **Data Auditing** in the iShare architecture involves tracking and monitoring data exchanges to ensure compliance with established agreements and standards. The framework includes components for provenance and traceability, which are essential for maintaining audit trails of data transactions; (iii) **Data Monetization** within the iShare architecture involves creating new revenue streams from data by enabling its use and exchange in a controlled environment. The framework supports various data monetization strategies, such as Data-as-a-Service and Insight-as-a-Service, which allow organizations to sell raw data or processed insights to third parties.

The EU project Open-DEI has also published a paper on “Design Principles for Data Spaces (Open-DEI)”, which describes various building blocks related to data auditing, logging, data trading, and monetization, including several technical, governance, and business components. For instance, it specifies data auditing and logging building blocks such as technical building blocks (e.g., provenance and traceability and identity management) and Operational Building Blocks (e.g., Audit Trails and Access and Usage Control Policies). It also specified business building blocks for data trading, including data marketplaces, smart contracts, and data exchange APIs. The specified data monetization building blocks also include data valuation methods, as well as billing and charging schemes.

1.3 Proclaimed Gaps and Limitations in Existing Implementations

The presentation of the above-listed building blocks demonstrates that most data spaces initiatives acknowledge data monetization functions as important elements of data spaces and provide some means for implementing monetization and trading schemes. Nevertheless, the status of current

implementations reveals a series of gaps in current approaches and knowledge, including technical, operational and legal/regulatory challenges.

Most of the presented architectures outlined high-level components that can support data trading and monetization. However, they rarely come with complete and integrated implementation, which outlines a gap in the data monetization features of existing middleware platforms for data spaces. The implementation of data monetization and data trading schemes is technically complex, as it cannot be based on conventional centralized infrastructures (e.g., cloud infrastructures) managed by a single entity. Rather they need to integrate decentralized models for managing data assets into data spaces, based on technologies like blockchain. This is a complex task considering also the need for implementing robust encryption methods and managing distributed networks. The latter are resource-intensive tasks which typically require specialized expertise. Furthermore, most of the presented building blocks provide baseline models and infrastructures for data valuation and monetization without adequate emphasis on market mechanisms for data trading.

One of the main operational challenges for data spaces that account for monetization lies in the lack of effective and validated monetization models. It is still challenging to develop monetization models that align with business goals and customer expectations in a data space environment. Therefore, data space operators and data space participants often struggle to identify the most suitable monetization approach, whether it is selling data, improving products, or wrapping data with services. Likewise, there are no widespread implementation of data spaces enabled data markets that can support different trading schemes for data assets such as dynamic pricing and schemes that enable data to accrue value over time.

Developing viable economic models and ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks are additional significant challenges faced by data spaces enabled markets. Data marketplaces need to balance the interests of data providers, users, and intermediaries while adhering to legal requirements such as data protection regulations. This becomes particularly challenging in cases where participants come from different countries where diverse regulations apply.

1.4 Addressing the Lack of Support for Non-Trivial Monetization

As a result of the above-listed challenges and limitations, there is still a lack of data spaces implementations that support non-trivial monetization mechanisms such as schemes that go beyond flat pricing. Moreover, most data spaces implementation do not provide fully fledged implementations of data monetization components. The [Horizon Europe FAME project](#) addresses these limitations in the scope of a federated data marketplace implementation, which leverages data spaces concepts, adherence to EU values and regulations (e.g., data sovereignty), while providing support for non-trivial data monetization functionalities and schemes. Specifically, the FAME data marketplace provides an integrated infrastructure that enables trading and monetization of tokenized data assets over a blockchain infrastructure.

The purpose of this whitepaper is to provide a brief overview of the FAME data trading and monetization implementation, along with a short presentation of data trading, data monetization, and business modelling strategies that can be implemented over it. The presented infrastructure and monetization schemes could serve as a blueprint for stakeholder's parties interested in implementing such monetization strategies and business models over a data space. Hence, the present whitepaper aspires to initiate a discussion about the potential integration of elements of the FAME implementation within future version of reference architectures and of relevant information models.

The remainder of the whitepaper is structured as follows:

Section 2 following this introductory section introduces the FAME solution for trading and monetizing tokenized data assets over a decentralized blockchain infrastructure for data spaces.

Section 3 presents a set of trading and monetization strategies for data assets. These strategies can be supported by the FAME data trading infrastructure and some of them are already being implemented.

Section 4 concludes the whitepaper and presents follow-up steps and ways by which interested parties can engage in the standardization and wider use of FAME's approach.

2 The FAME Data Assets Trading and Monetization Infrastructure

2.1 FAME Data Trading Platform

The main goal of the FAME project is to develop a federated and decentralized data marketplace for embedded finance data assets. At the heart of the FAME marketplace lies a data space middleware platform, which comprises a decentralized blockchain-based system for trading and monetization of tokenized data assets. Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of this decentralized system, including its users (or actors) and the main interactions between them. The platform comprises seven main subsystems and interacts with two actors and one external database. The system's main purpose is to enable the trading of data assets between "Data Providers" and "Data Buyers."

Figure 1 – The FAME Federated Data Assets Trading Platform

Specifically, the system serves the following actors: (1) Data Providers, which offer data assets for trading on the platform; and (2) Data Buyers, which browse, discover and buy the offered data assets through the trading platform.

Moreover, the platform comprises the following external systems:

- **External Trading Data Assets Catalog**, which exchanges data assets information with the trading platform.
- **Legal Compliance Subsystem**, which provides legal and regulatory compliance services for the platform.

Central to the operation of the platform are the following subsystems:

- **Smart Contracts and Tokenisation Subsystem**, which handles the creation and management of smart contracts and tokens. It interacts with the Catalog Subsystem to receive asset metadata links and proofs. It also interacts with the Monetisation Subsystem for token monetisation.
- **Access Control Subsystem**, which manages access control to the platform.
- **Asset Pricing Subsystem**, which handles the pricing of assets.
- **Catalog Subsystem**, which manages centrally the data assets offered by Data Providers. It interfaces with all the actors and the majority of other subsystems to handle trades, pricing, access control, legal compliance, and asset metadata.
- **Monetisation Subsystem**, which manages the monetisation of tokens in the platform.
- **Trading Subsystem**, which manages trades on the platform.
- **Hyperledger Besu Blockchain**, which is used as a decentralized database to track and trace trades and for interaction with the Smart Contracts and Tokenisation Subsystem.

Figure 2 – FAME Smart Contract and Asset Tokenization System

The "Smart Contracts and Tokenization Subsystem" is illustrated in Figure 2 and forms the core of the Federated Data Asset Trading Platform. The specific responsibilities and functionalities of the subsystem, including its interactions with various other components are as follows:

- **Private T&M Application:** A private API gateway for secure interaction with internal FAME modules.
- **Public T&M Application:** A publicly exposed API gateway for external users to interact with the trading and monetization system.
- **Payment Token Contract:** Implements ERC-20 standards for minting and burning payment tokens.
- **Data Assets Contracts:** ERC-1155 tokens representing ownership of data access across different business models.
- **Offerings Contract:** A ledger of trade offers implemented as an ERC-721 contract for cataloging and purchasing data access tokens.
- **Bourse (Trading) Contract:** Facilitates swapping of payment tokens for data asset tokens in transactions.
- **Governance Contract:** Oversees the minting and burning of payment tokens and interacts with escrow, trading, and payment contracts to ensure system integrity.
- **Escrow Contract:** Holds payment tokens securely for deferred transactions, supporting business models like Pay-As-You-Use (PAYU).

The system is integrated with a **Private Blockchain** (e.g. Hyperledger Besu), providing an Ethereum Virtual Machine environment for provenance and traceability of transactions. Interactions between external users, FAME actors, and blockchain components are enabled via the REST API gateways. The architecture ensures modularity, security, and scalability while supporting diverse data consumption models.

The components that represent contracts for standards-based tokenized assets (e.g., [ERC-721](#), [ERC-1155](#)). For instance, the implementation of the ERC-721 protocol is accompanied by “offering” components that initializes a blockchain trading environment for offerings based on minting of an ERC-721 token for it. At the same time, the component supports functionalities for removing offering from the system. Likewise, Escrow Contract components handle the holding and using the ERC-20 Payment Tokens, based on functions for using Payment Tokens based on the used number of services by the user, for depositing payment tokens to the Escrow and for withdrawing the amount of Payment Tokens by the user.

2.2 The FAME Price Advisory Tool (PAT)

2.2.1 PAT Overview

One of the highlights of the platform is the provision of support for a data-driven pricing advisory mechanism (i.e., the FAME Price Advisory Tool (PAT)), which leverages issuer-provided data, stakeholder survey responses, and historical pricing realization analytics. Specifically, PAT includes a RESTful open API that offers price recommendations for assets and digital products based on user inputs. It aims to extract both subjective and objective influences impacting the final price. Additionally, it provides the functionality to offer price ranges based on similar assets for which prices have historically been determined. Thus, the end-user can view the potential price range within which the price of an asset or digital product may fluctuate. FAME’s PAT uses a user-questionnaire with specific questions to calculate intrinsic value of the digital asset (i.e., based on a Value-based pricing approach) for two broad groups: datasets and digital products. The value of the digital asset is practically based on several parameters, including the estimated cost for the customer, the quality of the data asset (measured according to its accuracy, validity, and completeness), the cost of the asset’s creation, the volume of customers, the uniqueness of the asset, as well as its environmental

sustainability (CO₂). FAME's unique approach for the formulation of a realistic suggestion for the price of a digital asset is considering the Cost-Plus Pricing strategy, which enriches the profit margin element based on the value-based approach. Furthermore, the PAT is providing information on the price of similar assets. The overarching vision of the PAT strategy is to incorporate interest-based metrics derived from the quantification of user interactions (clicks) with analogous data assets of the platform. Nonetheless, the determination of asset pricing within the FAME ecosystem remains the prerogative of the client.

Based on the above-listed infrastructure FAME supports the implementation of a wide range of data pricing and monetization schemes, which are outlined in the following section.

2.2.2 Assessing Similarity Among Data Assets

The PAT considers the properties of a focal data asset in comparison to other data assets so as to recommend a price for focal data asset. The pricing advisory tool of FAME utilizes the information available about data assets in the form of numeric, logical, ordinal or text data to derive similar data assets and considers their prices from historical trades to recommend the price of focal data asset. This similarity between data assets is derived as follows:

2.2.2.1 Similarity based on logical characteristics of data assets

Given the binary characteristics of data assets such as if the data asset is a sensor data or not, if there are copyrights associated with the data asset, and so on generalization of Hamming distance can be used to compute similarity among data assets on these aspects. Suppose there are p logical characteristics of data assets available then similarity can be mathematically represented as follows:

$$SM_{logical} = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^{l=p} w_l (DA_l^i == DA_l^j)}{|p|} \quad (1)$$

where w_l indicates weight of a logical characteristic and DA^l represents a logical characteristic.

2.2.2.2 Similarity based on ordinal characteristics of data assets

Some characteristics of data assets could be available as ordinal characteristics on a Likert scale such as how suitable is a data asset for a particular application, how credible is the source of data asset etc. Similarity computation based on these aspects can be performed using the generalization of cosine similarity. If there are q ordinal characteristics of data assets available, then following formulation can be used to compute similarity about these ordinal characteristics:

$$SM_{ordinal} = \frac{\sum_{o=1}^{o=q} w_o DA_o^i \times w_o DA_o^j}{\sqrt{\sum_{o=1}^{o=q} (w_o DA_o^i)^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{o=1}^{o=q} (w_o DA_o^j)^2}} \quad (2)$$

where w_o indicates weight of an ordinal characteristic and DA^o represents an ordinal characteristic.

2.2.2.3 Similarity based on numeric characteristics of data assets

Moreover, the information about characteristics of data assets such as size of the data asset, resources required to assemble the data asset, and so on may be available in numeric form. If there are r such characteristics of data assets available, similarity computation among them can be performed by using the generalization of cosine similarity as follows:

$$SM_{numeric} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{n=r} w_n \log(DA_i^n) \times w_n \log(DA_j^n)}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{n=r} (w_n \log(DA_i^n))^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{n=r} (w_n \log(DA_j^n))^2}} \quad (3)$$

where w_n indicates the weight of each numeric characteristic and DA^n represents an ordinal characteristic. In the above formulation, the numeric values are adjusted using logarithmic transformation before cosine similarity computation.

2.2.2.4 Similarity based on textual data associated with data assets

The text data could also be associated with non-textual data assets in the form of their description and/or title. Thus, similarity based on textual data can be computed between data assets using metrics based on lexical similarity or semantic similarity etc. The lexical text similarity includes metrics such as cosine similarity, Jaccard similarity, Sørensen-Dice coefficient, and Levenshtein distance etc. Semantic text similarity includes approaches based on word or sentence embeddings, contextual language models, sentence transformers etc. In FAME, we derive semantic text similarity between data assets using BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers).

Figure 3 - An overview of the role of similarity measurement in pricing advisory in FAME

3 Data Pricing and Monetization Schemes

3.1 The Peculiarities of Data as a new Asset Class

Data assets represent a new asset class, which is not adequately covered by classic asset pricing tools. One of the main reasons for this is that data has a large private value component. The value of a data asset to one investor or organization is not the exactly the same as its value to another.

Valuations for the same data asset can differ by many orders of magnitude. Hence, it is not practical to compute a return or estimating a covariance with market returns in order to produce a valuation of the asset. Moreover, in the scope of the data economy there are new business models and new entry barriers. Hence, monetary revenue may not accurately reveal the value that the firm is generating or accumulating. For instance, many prominent data-intensive firms (e.g., Amazon, Uber) have had negative balance sheets for several years, yet they remained extremely valuable because of the data assets they were accumulating. Overall firms that do manage to accumulate and monetize their data can earn a dominant market position.

It is also important that new data technologies, AI and machine learning are technologies that enable prediction i.e., they use data to forecast outcomes. This forecasting ability makes data different from other assets and inputs. Data can be used to forecast demand, or even to forecast asset returns (e.g., in finance applications).

As outlined, unlike financial assets, data assets are not equally valuable to all. This dispersion in private valuations changes the conventional understanding of data markets because when values are highly dispersed and the market price of data changes, few customers have valuations between the old and new price. Hence, few customers change their data demand in response to the price change. This leads to a low-price elasticity of aggregate data demand. Furthermore, data can be an essential input for research and development of new products. This type of data is often a byproduct of economic activity. Data is non-rivalrous in consumption, which means that it can be used by multiple parties at the same time without any degradation in its utility or value. This differentiates it from physical goods, where consumption by one party reduces availability for others. For most businesses, these characteristics of data open up unique opportunities for monetization and scalability. However, these special characteristics of data ask for careful consideration of pricing strategies to ensure that the value of data assets are captured effectively.

3.2 FAME Pricing Strategies

Table 1 provides an overview of different pricing strategies that are considered and implemented in FAME. The strategies consider the previous-listed valuation-related peculiarities of data assets. Effective data monetization requires a comprehensive understanding of both the intrinsic value of data and the perceived value to customers. Using the presented strategies businesses can set prices that reflect the true worth of their data assets. The non-rival nature of data plays a crucial role in these strategies, allowing for scalability and flexible pricing models that can maximize revenue and customer satisfaction at the same time.

Table 1 – Pricing Strategies considered and supported in the scope of the FAME Data Trading Platform

Pricing Strategy	Formula	Description
Competitive Benchmarking	$P = P_{\text{avg_market}} \times (1 + V_{\text{relative}}/100)$	Setting prices based on the average market price of similar data products, adjusted for the relative

		<p>value your data provides. Ensures competitive positioning and reflects the unique benefits your data offers.</p> <p>Non-rivalry allows benchmarking against a wide range of competitors without diminishing value through increased usage.</p>
Cost-Plus Pricing	$P=C+(C\times M)$	<p>Adding a profit margin to the total costs associated with producing and delivering the data. Ensures all costs are covered and a profit margin is achieved.</p> <p>Types of Costs: Data Acquisition, Data Processing, Infrastructure, Development and Maintenance, Compliance and Security, Operational, Depreciation and Amortization, R&D</p>
Value-Based Pricing	$P=V_{\text{customer}}\times(1+M/100)$	<p>Setting prices based on the perceived value to the customer. Requires understanding customer usage and benefits.</p> <p>Methods: Customer Surveys and Interviews, Value Workshops, Case Studies and Testimonials, Competitive Analysis, ROI Analysis, Expert Panels and Focus Groups, Customer Usage Data and Analytics, Pilots and Trials</p>
Usage-Based Pricing	$P=R\times U$	<p>Charging customers based on the amount of data they consume. Aligns the cost with usage, making it attractive for customers with varying needs.</p> <p>Non-rivalry allows flexible and scalable usage without incurring additional marginal costs.</p>
Dynamic Pricing	$P=P_{\text{base}}\times(1+D/100)$	<p>Adjusting prices based on real-time supply and demand conditions. Maximizes revenue by capturing the willingness to pay of different customers at different times.</p> <p>Data can be simultaneously accessed by multiple users, optimizing revenue without affecting availability.</p>
Auction-Based Pricing	$P=\max_{f_0}(B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n)$	<p>Allowing customers to bid for data, letting the market determine the price. Effective for unique or highly demanded datasets.</p> <p>Non-rivalry ensures data can be sold to the highest bidder while remaining available for others if appropriate.</p>
Customer Segmentation	$P_s=V_s\times(1+M_s/100)$	<p>Segmenting customers based on their specific needs and willingness to pay. Tailors pricing strategies for different market segments.</p> <p>Non-rivalry ensures data can be segmented and priced differently for various customer groups without limiting availability.</p>

Along with the choice of a suitable pricing strategy, data asset owner and data service must consider the sales model (e.g., Subscription, Freemium Model with Tiered Pricing) that they wish to apply to their assets. In this direction, Table 2 illustrates some of the models for selling and distributing data assets (e.g., business models) considered and applied in FAME. These business models complement the presented pricing strategies towards a complete approach to pricing and monetization that works in practice and for different types of data assets.

Table 2 – Price-setting based on business model applied

Subscription Pricing	$P_{\text{monthly}}=V_{\text{annua}}/12$	Charging a recurring fee for continuous access to data. Provides a steady revenue stream while allowing unlimited access to multiple users.
Freemium Model with Tiered Pricing	$P_{\text{premium}}=V_{\text{premium}}\times(1+M/100)$	Offering basic data access for free, with advanced features or larger datasets available at a cost. Attracts a broad user base initially, converting a portion to paying customers.
Bundling and Packaging	$P_{\text{bundle}}=\sum_{i=1}^n P_i \times (1 - D_{\text{bundle}}/100)$	Selling data along with other complementary services or datasets. Creates perceived added value and drives higher sales volumes. Non-rivalry allows bundling different datasets or services without additional cost implications.

4 Conclusions and Standardization Outlook

Pricing, trading, and monetizing data assets can be very important functionalities for modern data spaces, as they can incentivize data owners to participate in a data space ecosystem. This is the reason why most data spaces architectures and implementations acknowledge the importance of pricing and monetization functions, while also specifying technical and operational building blocks for developing and deploying data monetization functions. Nevertheless, the practical implementation of these building blocks is usually trivial and not connected to real-life pricing strategies. Most importantly, these practical implementations are rarely integrated over a decentralized data management platform for trading and pricing assets without the involvement of a centralized trusted third party.

The FAME project introduces solutions that address the above-listed challenges and limitations, including:

- A decentralized blockchain-based infrastructure for sharing data and metadata about data assets, in ways that enable their tokenization, monetization and trading across different data spaces actors, including data providers and data buyers. In the scope of this blockchain, data assets can be traded based on fungible and non-fungible tokens that can accrue value over time.
- A price advisory tool that facilitates the production of recommendations about the fair pricing of different data assets. These recommendations can help data providers in devising effective prices for the data.
- A collection of pricing strategies that consider the unique characteristics of data assets in terms of their valuation, including the unique value of each asset for different market participants and the low-price elasticity of aggregate data demand when trading data assets. The FAME blockchain-based trading platform supports the practical implementation of these pricing strategies.

The FAME solution can serve as a blueprint for similar implementations, which outlines the potential value of the FAME blockchain-infrastructure for data monetization and data trading in data space, beyond the specific implementation of the project. Likewise, the different components of the FAME assets trading platform (e.g., the different types of decentralized smart contracts introduced) could be standardized as new monetization building blocks in the context of standards-based reference architectures and information models for data spaces. As such they can provide extensions to the IDS reference architecture model and to respective models used in the Data Spaces Support Centre. Using the present whitepaper as starting point, FAME encourages relevant discussions and plans to present its approach to relevant events that are co-organized or coordinated by the International Data Spaces Association.

References

1. Y. Lu, X. Huang, Y. Dai, S. Maharjan and Y. Zhang, "Blockchain and federated learning for privacy- preserved data sharing in industrial IoT", IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 4177-4186, 2019.
2. R. Song, B. Xiao, Y. Song, S. Guo and Y. Yang, "A Survey of Blockchain-Based Schemes for Data Sharing and Exchange," in IEEE Transactions on Big Data, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1477-1495, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TBDDATA.2023.3293279.
3. Santin, G., Skarbovsky, I., Fournier, F., & Lepri, B. (2022). A Framework for Verifiable and Auditable Collaborative Anomaly Detection. IEEE Access, 10, 82896-82909.
4. Nagel L., Lycklama D. (2021): Design Principles for Data Spaces. Position Paper. Version 1.0. Berlin, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>.
5. Steinbuss S., Ottradovetz K., Langkau J., Punter M. et al. (2021) IDSA Rule Book. International Data Spaces Association, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5658294>.
6. Qusai Ramadan, Zeyd Boukhers, Muath Alshaikh, Christoph Lange, and Jan Jurjens. 2023. Data Trading and Monetization: Challenges and Open Research Directions. In The International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems (ICFNDS '23), December 21--22, 2023, Dubai, United Arab Emirates. ACM, New York, NY, USA 8 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3644713.3644758>.
7. Bechtsis, D., Tsolakis, N., Iakovou, E., & Vlachos, D. (2021). Data-driven secure, resilient and sustainable supply chains: gaps, opportunities, and a new generalised data sharing and data monetisation framework. International Journal of Production Research, 60, 4397 - 4417.
8. Al-Saif, N., Ahmad, R.W., Salah, K., Yaqoob, I., Jayaraman, R., & Omar, M.A. (2021). Blockchain for Electric Vehicles Energy Trading: Requirements, Opportunities, and Challenges. IEEE Access, PP, 1-1.